

LEGAL ASPECTS

OF ACCESS TO AND REUSE OF
SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION IN **GREECE**

A KR21 REPORT

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Note

Greek names and references, except Law titles, have been transliterated according to the ALA-LC Romanization standard, using the Transliteration Service of the National Library of Greece (<https://transliteration.nlg.gr>). Law titles have been translated in English to relate with European legislation, where available.

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Abbreviations

EIS: European Innovation Scoreboard

EKT: National Documentation Center

ELIDEK: Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (Hellēniko Hidryma Ereunas & Kainotomias)

ERA: European Research Area

ERC: European Research Council

ESETEK: National Council for Research, Technology and Innovation (Ethniko Symvoulío Ereunas, Technologias kai Kainotomias)

GGEK: General Secretariat for Research and Innovation (Genikē Grammateia Ereunas kai Kainotomias)

HE: Higher Education

HEI: Higher Education Institutions

HOSI: Hellenic Open Science Initiative

NRI: National Research Infrastructure

PAKEK: Panepistēmiako Kentro Ereunas kai Kainotomias (University Centers of Research and Innovation)

PPP: Public-Private Partnerships

R&D: Research and Development

R&I: Research and Innovation

RFO: Research Funding Organization

RPO: Research Performing Organization

SPR: Secondary Publishing Right

1. Introduction

Research and Innovation are key instruments for the expansion of our scientific knowledge, the improvement of living conditions and social, cultural, and economic growth. For countries like Greece that still experience the effects of the fiscal shrinking of the previous decade, research and innovation are also a necessity for the social stability and cohesion. The effects of fiscal measures have been quite evident at the regional level and Greece is a country that has lived with the consequences of mass outward migration of its productive (wo)manpower.¹ As stated in the Letta [1] and Draghi [2] reports, freedom of knowledge circulation in the European Union is a prerequisite of common growth and development.

We hypothesize that revising the legal framework and maximizing legal flows of information in order to deliver on this freedom would make it possible to improve the research environment. If Greek researchers can conduct their work in parity to their peers in other countries, this will reduce the incentive to move away.

This report has been commissioned by the Knowledge Rights 21 National Coordinator for Greece, Giorgos Glossiotis, in the frame of the 2025 Annual Plan. The study has been conducted by the Scholarly Communication Unit (henceforth EESC, from the abbreviation of the mixed alphabet of “Epistēmōnikē Epikoinōnēsē Scholarly Communication”, <https://scholarly.heal-link.gr>) of the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link (HEAL-Link, <https://www.heal-link.gr>), the consortium of Greek academic libraries. EESC operates from the Library and Information Center of the University of Patras, Greece, as a branch of HEAL-Link. According to the statutes of the consortium, its aim is “...to inform the Greek academic community about issues of Open Access and Open Science, to provide support on the actions of these topics, to monitor the international developments, and to promote all beneficial measures – technical, legal or political nature – for the wide provision of research content.”

The aim of the report is twofold: first, to summarize the current legislative framework for research and innovation in Greece and outline the challenges it represents to an open system of knowledge circulation. The second aim is to provide to all interested stakeholders evidence of the obstacles and the perceptions that Greek researchers face when attempting to access and to reuse information for research purposes. The scope of the report is open access to scientific publications (as a manifestation of the research intellect of the country), to data (as primary products that feed research processes), and to infrastructures (as the computing mechanisms that allow storage, preservation, operation, and dissemination of research outputs).

The report is divided into four parts. First, we establish a profile of the Greek research system and relate this to that of other European countries. The comparative assessment of these figures indicates some areas where reform to

¹ The World Population Review (<https://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/greece>) provides a score of 4.1 to Greece in the Human Flight and Brain Drain Index, a number constantly rising from 2018. According to its report 46 people migrate daily, although no one can conclude for reasons related to this study.

policies and legislation could be beneficial for research. Second, we explore the main Laws, which come from many sources, that govern the activities for research in the country. Third, we report the main findings of a survey that EESC conducted in the spring of 2025 to help us understand how the Greek researchers perceive aspects of openness in accessing and reusing research assets in a lawful way. Finally, we provide some recommendations addressed both to the main research stakeholders and to their research libraries.

2. The profile of Greek research

One has to understand that knowledge flows in Greece are not affected only by legal measures. As in other countries, there certainly are legislative measures, such as Laws and Decrees that govern the formal regulatory framework for the main stakeholders, but also soft measures, such as policies and recommendations. However, one of the most critical factors is the lack of a coherent national policy, as well as the presence of inconsistent practices, siloed cultures, bureaucracy, and conservatism. Spyros Artavanis-Tsakonas, the former Chair of the National Council for Research, Technology and Innovation (Ethniko Symvoulío Ereunās, Technologías kai Kainotomías, abbrev. ESETEK in Greek), who resigned in 2024, mentioned that “research in universities is subjected to different regulations than research in research institutions, as if the nature of the research process is different” [3]. Indeed, research policy in Greece is currently under the Ministry of Development, whereas in 2011-2018, it was under the Ministry of Education, Religious Affairs and Sports (henceforth Ministry of Education). Greek research institutions are swapping positions between these two Ministries, whereas universities, one of the main pillars of basic research, operate solely under the Ministry of Education. The Ministry of Development has delegated the management of research, technological development, and innovation policies to the General Secretariat for Research and Innovation (Genikē Grammateia Ereunās kai Kainotomías, abbrev. GGEK), which is supported by the strategic guidance of ESETEK. Together with GGEK, the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (Hellēniko Hidryma Ereunās & Kainotomías, abbrev. ELIDEK) is the main Research Funding Organization (RFO).

Like in other countries, research in Greece is divided into basic and in applied research. According to Law 4386/2016 that establishes the relevant framework, basic research is defined as “theoretical or experimental work that has as its primary goal the knowledge and understanding of the world and the production of new knowledge.” At the same time, applied (or industrial) research is defined as “planned research or critical investigation of a field aimed at acquiring new knowledge and skills for the development of new products, processes or services or for the significant improvement of existing products, processes or services.”

GGEK has a crucial role in the “National Strategy for Research, Technological Development, and Innovation,” encompassing both the “National Strategy for Smart Specialization” and the “Basic Research Strategy.” The Strategy is bolstered by the ambitions of the Greek Government for the digital transformation and financial priorities of the “Recovery and Resilience Plan - Greece 2.0.” Altogether, several measures aim to mobilize R&D activities in the private sector: the friendly taxation regime for R&D, the encouragement of collaboration with Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), and the development of a fertile startup cultivation system, etc. The Strategy also considers the European Research Area and the Horizon Europe policies.

There are several indicators to assess the research performance of a country, but the scattering of sources, types of information (bibliometric, indexes, compound indicators, etc.) and the incompatibility of the period that they cover mean that these do not present comparable views. Furthermore, the State should

invest in a consistent way, be visionary, going beyond mere figures, and should translate to an actual transformation of research culture.

In our presentation, we use data from the European Research Area, EUROSTAT, the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), SciVal (<https://www.scival.com>), and the National Documentation Center (Ethniko Kentro Tekmēriōsēs, abbrev. EKT), to create a simple list with the most recent generic indicators to create the profile of Greek research, compared only to the European Union's average (where possible).

- **R&D Investments:** According to EUROSTAT, Greece invests 1.49% of its Gross Domestic Product for R&D. This falls below the EU average, which is 2.22% [4]. The 2023 data of EKT show that the national R&D intramural expenditure is concentrated mainly in the business & enterprises and the HE sectors, 49.3% and 21% respectively [5].
- **Personnel:** Greece has improved its score of personnel working on R&D, 1.6% of the economically active population, compared to a 1.55% mean rate across the EU. This shows an increase in the labor force of R&D, driven mainly by 45.5% of the HE and 30.9% of the business & enterprises sector. However, there is a concern regarding job-to-job mobility and female representation. The country is 18th overall in the She Figures Index, with a score of 71.4 and with major concerns in women career progression and decision-making [6].
- **Basic research:** Indicators like European Research Council funding show that Greece is falling behind its competitors for ERC grants, with only two in 882 projects in 2024 [7]. In the Horizon Europe programme however, Greece performs far better, coming seventh in the list of countries that signed grants (n=2114) [8].
- **Innovation:** EIS shows that, despite improvement since 2017, Greece remains at the bottom of the moderate innovators group with a decrease of 2.9 points from 2024. The profile highlights that the strong financial support by the government over the last years has been halted (-4.4 points in the index since last year) and that the linkages between enterprises are weak (-36.2 since 2024) [9].
- **Research Outputs:** By outputs, we searched for publication and data figures, with special attention to open. Based on data from SciVal, 52.3% of Greek scholarly output is open access compared to 58.8% for the EU27 (other sources indicate that the Greek percentage might be lower, 42%). Based on the same source, synergies of RPOs and the industrial sector show that co-authored research publications represent 4.1% of the total output compared to 3.8% of the total for the EU27 in the period 2019-2023. Greek research outputs as a whole have an average Field Weighted Citation Impact of 1.43 in this period compared to the EU27 median of 1.13.
- **Infrastructures.** According to the ERA country report, Greece outperforms the EU average with 28 National Research Infrastructures (NRIs), but performs below the EU average of 1.82% of GDP when it comes to national expenditure on such infrastructures (0.96%) [10]. A final experts' report underlined the lack of data policies and services by mentioning "NRIs would have benefited from support for developing research data platforms that nurture the full lifecycle of scientific data management, processing, sharing and reuse" [11].

- **Knowledge valorization:** SciVal reports that Greece registered 85 patents in all Offices in 2023, whereas the EU27 average figure was 120.7 per country. It is notable though that this small number of patents are competitive according to the Patent-Citation metric, with an indicator of 2.7 compared to the European one of 3.2.²

These figures indicate that while there is strong potential in the Greek research system, there are several factors that hold back its stability and progress. For instance, despite the fact that there are low records for knowledge valorization, it is quite competitive in terms of scientific impact. Public HEIs are poorly funded, especially compared to financial support that the business & enterprise sector receives. Even though they perform as the engine of research, public institutions operate in conditions that jeopardize viability and sustainability.

In particular, the recent ERA country report showcases the inability of Greece to articulate and implement a strong Open Science policy and develop a framework that commits energy and resources to engage the entire research system. For instance, while there is a solid set of research infrastructures, and a well-regarded system that enables the participation of Greek RPOs in Horizon Europe and WIDERA programs, this is not supported by corresponding services and policies. Therefore, in a research context that does not support research curiosity and knowledge circulation to flourish, these important achievements risk having the fate of the 2004 Olympic Games infrastructures: once useful but now devastated by the absence of strategic vision, support, and maintenance.

As the ERA report implies in many places, several good initiatives start bottom up, but with the bureaucratic processes, the difficulty in feeding and retaining talent, the legal uncertainty and more, they remain at risk.

² The definition according to SciVal is “the patent-citation counts divided by the total scholarly output of the university for that period and multiplied by 1,000”, see https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/28201/supporthub/scival/p/10961/28201/.

3. Legislation in Greece affecting research

3.1. National laws

As in other countries, laws that affect research come from two sources: the law for copyrighted works, which is the responsibility of Ministry of Culture, and the laws governing RPOs, which are responsibility of various Ministries across the years, including those of Education, Research and Development, and Digital Governance.

Research outputs are considered intellectual works, which are protected by the provisions of the Law 2121/93 (as amended and in force), the basic law of intellectual property issues in Greece, which, with its amendments by 4996/2022 Law, incorporates the transposition of EU Directives 789/2019 (SatCab) and 790/2019 (Digital Single Market). The Law mentions that “The term work shall designate any original intellectual literary, artistic or scientific creation, expressed in any form...,” which broadly covers scientific publications and data.

However, the Greek legislation does not focus on matters of access to and reuse of scientific publications per se. The measures that govern access to and reuse of scientific works are the exceptions and limitations for research and education applying to all types of work, as performed by non-for-profit organizations and within the range of their jurisdictions, including lawful reproduction and text and data mining. However, in the frame of a law that is directed at the protection, often excessive, of any intellectual work, there is a risk of coming into conflict with contemporary needs for growth and development, as well as with fundamental freedoms like access to information society, research and education as well as competition. This is particularly so when it comes to facilitating any sort of use for research outside of the purely non-commercial, for example in the context of collaborations with industry. The comparison by CopyrightExceptions.eu reflects that the Greek national transposition of several EU Directives is to a great extent restrictive.³

On the other hand, the laws governing RPOs mainly describe their structure and operations and do not explicitly deal with rights management. The current legal framework has a strong inclination towards linking research with industrial policy goals and therefore facilitates Public-Private Partnerships (henceforth PPPs) for knowledge and technology transfer. However, in this complex system, these Laws nonetheless set out specific priorities that may be undermined by restrictive practices countenanced by copyright law. For instance, Law 4386/2016 about research mentions that the Regional Councils of Research and Innovation have the responsibility to provide “aid for research infrastructures to which access is ensured on a transparent and non-discriminatory basis”. This is an important commitment to equal participation in information society.

³ The Copyright Exceptions (www.copyrightexceptions.eu) website collects and labels data from the 2001 Copyright in the Information Society Directive, the 2019 Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive, the 2012 Orphan Works Directive, and the 2017 Marrakesh Directive. While the Law 4996/2022 has not been yet labeled by Copyright Exceptions team, it is reckoned that the transposition is quite restrictive.

However, this principle of access may be undermined by the (over)-application of copyright protections. The same Law (4386/2016) defines intellectual property as “the intellectual and industrial property and in particular the property and moral rights arising from the works that contain them, know-how, trademarks, patents and utility certificates.” The Law goes on to define innovation as the “the exploitation of existing or new knowledge or the transformation of an idea into a product or process or service.” It is therefore signifying the need to use knowledge as an instrument of further development and growth elsewhere, while for research and development it mentions that one of the prime drivers is the increase of the knowledge stock for the purpose of developing new applications. Finally, the Law allows research centers to commercially exploit their intellectual works through ETAKs (projects of Research, Technological Advancement and Innovation) or spin-offs. The management of intellectual property should be embodied in their internal regulations, including types of compensation for the contributing researchers.

The recent Law for Universities, 4957/2022, explicitly mentions that Universities should be linked with the developmental needs of the country and contribute to the “National Strategy for Research, Technological Advancement and Innovation.” The Law describes the ability of several units of Universities, such as their laboratories and University Centers of Research and Innovation (Panepistēmiaka Kentra Ereunas kai Kainototomias, PAKEK), to conduct basic and experimental research. Critical for the system of knowledge transfer is the establishment of Technology Transfer Units that amongst other things are responsible for support to researchers on matters of intellectual property management and the portfolio of intellectual property rights, such as patents trademarks, software, etc.

The Law also describes “Industrial PhDs,” which are doctoral programmes that are conducted together with enterprises and industries. While Industrial PhDs in this period are funded by EU sources, through the Recovery and Resilience Facility, there are no provisions about policies that govern the sharing of outputs, and the delineation of the intellectual property rights management is part of the memoranda of collaboration that the HEIs and the industries sign together.

Spin-offs are important establishments for knowledge and technology transfer, as well as for the exploitation of research. Law 4864/2021 on strategic investments and spin-offs defines the role of the latter in relation to HEIs and research centers: their role is definitely aimed at the commercial exploitation of research outputs, mentioning that their activity is not related to the main research and educational missions of their institutions. However, the institution can provide space, equipment, and infrastructure for a specific period of time, with renewal rights. This raises concerns about their coverage by exceptions and limitations that would otherwise allow for use of information and knowledge systems for research and education.

Table 1 presents the legislative framework that affects research in Greece. The left column lists the European legislation, Directives and Regulations that regulate aspects of research. Where available their national transposition acts are listed in right column, together with the national legislation that is in force. Links provide access to the EUR-Lex and the National Printing House entries, respectively.

Table 1: European and National legislation affecting research.

FEK= Phyllo Ephēmeridos Kyvernēseōs (the Government's Gazette), followed by the Section and the Number/Year. N= Nomos (Law)	
EU Legislation	National Legislation
	N. 1733, FEK A' 171/1987. Technology transfer, inventions, technological innovation and establishment of an Atomic Energy Committee
	N. 2121, FEK A' 25/1993. Copyright, Related Rights and Cultural Matters. Amended by N. 4996, FEK A' 218/2022.
Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases	
Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society	§ 81 N. 3057, FEK A' 239/2002. Harmonization with Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society
	N. 4386, FEK A' 83/2016. Research settings and other provisions
Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast)	N. 4727, FEK A' 184/2020. Digital Governance (Incorporation into Greek Law of Directive (EU) 2016/2102 and Directive (EU) 2019/1024) - Electronic Communications (Incorporation into Greek Law of Directive (EU) 2018/1972) and other provisions
	N. 4864, FEK A' 237/2021. Strategic investments and improvement of the investment environment through the acceleration of procedures in private and strategic investments, creation of a framework for spin-off companies and other urgent provisions for development
Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Text with EEA relevance)	N. 4996, FEK A' 218/2022. Establishing rules on the exercise of copyright and related rights applicable to certain online broadcasts of broadcasting organisations and retransmissions of television and radio programmes, with the maintenance of a high level of protection of copyright and related rights in the digital single market and with the public lending right and the reproduction of an additional copy by non-profit libraries or archives - Amendment of L. 2121/1993 and L. 4481/2017 - Transposition of Directives (EU) 2019/789, (EU) 2019/790 and 2006/115/EC

	N. 4957, FEK A' 141/2022. New horizons in Higher Education Institutions: strengthening the quality, functionality and connection of HEIs with society and other provisions
Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	
Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	
Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	
Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	N. 5099, FEK A' 48/2024. Adoption of measures for the implementation of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on the single market for digital services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC ("Digital Services Act") and other provisions of the Ministry of Digital Governance
Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	N. 5188, FEK A' 49/2025. Measures implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/868 (data governance act) - Designation of a competent authority for the application of Regulation (EU) 2024/903 (Interoperable Europe Regulation) - Electronic application "mystreet" - Arrangements for the promotion of digital transformation and other provisions. data governance act)

What is missing from the current legislation are instruments concerned specifically with access to and reuse of information. For instance, the concept of Secondary Publishing Rights (SPRs), which refers to “the rights of researchers and their employers to reuse a work after the first publication of a formal version; in this case to republish it on an infrastructure that by its nature (public and not-for-profit) is coherent with the (public) nature of the funding source” [12], is entirely absent. However, currently, there are eight European countries that have an SPR and the latest countries that have joined this movement are Slovenia and Bulgaria,

aiming to strengthen the position of the authors to reuse information that they have intellectually and otherwise produced with public funds and for non-for-profit purposes.

3.2. Policy initiatives

Scholarly practices, as mentioned above, are primarily based on the discipline-specific codes and conventions, which create social/moral obligations and rights. The role of contractual agreements in shaping these practices cannot be ignored, especially when one considers that they are tied up with invisible constructs, such as professional and/or social assessment, limit options, and steer decisions to specific ‘privileged’ outlets.

There are potential institutional policy measures that can be taken in order to counterbalance the harmful effect of excessive application of intellectual property regulation. However, in no Greek academic or research institutions is there a policy that includes strong rights retention provisions, as exist in other countries, nor does any RFO participate in the emblematic PlanS [13], which also promotes such provisions. For reference, rights retention refers to measures in institutional policies “...promoting the practice of retaining sufficient rights for academic works of institutions’ employees to make the work immediately openly accessible and reusable” [14].

The “Digital Transformation Bible 2020-2025” is the first step towards creating a supportive context for policy interventions. The “Bible” explicitly mentions areas of Open Science where there is a need for investment, such as the reinforcement of the national research network, the upgrade of national, thematic and institutional repositories and e-journals, open access to research infrastructures, and free availability and reuse of publicly funded research data, etc. [15]

In this context, the Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI, <https://www.hellenicopenscience.gr/>) has been established as a bottom-up approach, serving to introduce measures that promote openness in research and innovation. HOSI has published its Open Science Policy, which proposes main policy axes and implementation tools, and which is addressed to policy makers, RFOs, and RPOs [16]. The axes address the adoption of the policy, open access, research data, open software, and open infrastructures. However, the policy has not been implemented and according to several Open Science benchmarks, such as the ones provided by the Council for National Open Science Coordination [17] and OpenAIRE [18], the development and implementation of policies across RPOs is limited.

3.3. Legal definition of the rightsholder

In order to implement legislative measures in the research sector -either laws or policies- it is important to define who is the rightsholder, given that works are very frequently co-created in an environment that enjoys many degrees of freedom (and therefore ambiguity). Art 8 of Law 2121/93 defines that “the economic rights

in works created by employees under any work related to the public sector or a legal entity of public law in execution of their duties is ipso jure transferred to the employer, unless provided otherwise by contract.” However, in research and academia there are conditions that complicate the precise definition of a “dependent” research output (a product of an activity in the broad range of work) or a “service” (a product of a clearly ordered activity). Art. 65 of Law 4864/2021 is one of the few points in the research legislation that mentions “dependent and service inventions” in the context of patents and allocates ownership rights over intellectual property on outputs that were created in the context of a spin-off company. These terms are defined by internal regulation, which has provisions about the types of compensation that researchers enjoy. Should these not be defined, then the provisions of Law 1753/1987 on the Industrial Property Organization govern the output. In the provisions of art. 6 of this Law it is stated that patents that constitute service inventions are 100% owned by the respective institutions, while for dependent ones there is a 60/40% division for the researchers and their institutions.

3.4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the law for Intellectual Property does not take particular account of the specifics of the conditions under which research is conducted, but does create particular difficulties for research carried out through partnerships. This potentially has an impact on the competitiveness of Greek research, and so the rates of growth and development in the country. On the other hand, laws for research mainly lay the foundations and the structure of the ecosystem, rather than establishing instruments that can in principle facilitate research exposure and use. In practice, the Greek state has not taken any measures to regulate the scientific production of its citizens and claim returns on its own public investments. For instance, the country does not have legislation that provides SPRs to its authors, while institutions have not introduced rights retention policies, despite these being tools that would reduce legal uncertainty and engage authors with much more open practices. There is no top-down approach, which belies an awkwardness in managing these issues. Instead, regulation is mainly governed by two other “forces,” namely the contractual agreements between authors and publishers, and scholarly conventions and practices, which are primarily based on the ethics of each discipline.

4. Exploring perceptions and opinions on enablers and barriers

4.1. The problem of accessing information and data

The academic and research communities have long struggled with issues surrounding access to information and data. A mix of market dominance by a group of publishers, constrained finances and weak institutional negotiating power have limited the ability of researchers to access timely the scientific information that they need and has been produced by their peers. As a result, researchers live in a context of inequalities, which does not support a common approach to European growth. It is not within the scope of this report to outline how the market of scholarly communication and research information works, but it has to be noted that there is growing concern that copyright and contract law are enabling disputable market practices, even at the extreme edge of anti-trust, that prevent researchers from conducting effective research and risk public investments and taxpayers' money [19].

The problem of accessing available scientific knowledge is a global one. Even in wealthy economies, like the US, with high budgets and increased purchasing power, researchers are facing barriers to knowledge. According to the 2021 version of the survey by Ithaka S+R, a growing share of researchers in recent years find themselves unable to access the specific resources they need, leading them either to look for other versions that can be found freely, or simply to give up and have to rely on second-best options [20]. This shows that researchers have to compromise when it comes to material to support their research; they get what they can, not what they need.

A pan-European survey by the European Commission [21] has confirmed what is already well-known in the world of researchers: approximately 80% of researchers have been confronted with a lack of access to research outputs due to the lack of subscriptions and more than 60% due to other kinds of paywalls. Similarly, to their US peers, European researchers either look for free versions of the same resource or give up. Researchers mention also that there are “Legal uncertainties and administrative overhead associated with copyright, both restricted and Open Access” and they do not feel confident “about fair use (the right to use a copyrighted work under certain conditions without permission of the copyright owner) and the risk of copyright infringement.” These indicate that copyright legislation is creating more ambiguity than clarity about what researchers can do. The current landscape, instead of being straightforward, requires complex and delicate decisions, based on expert knowledge that researchers neither possess, nor should need to, given their other responsibilities.

Other previous surveys have indeed provided evidence that researchers are not well equipped with legal knowledge about their rights. In Italy, researchers have poor knowledge about copyright, and they do not exercise their re-publishing rights because of legal uncertainty [22]. Awareness of attempts to change the legislative framework (see Lege Gallo in 2018) is exceptionally low, while the main approach for publishing is fee-based, either as restricted access

(and therefore subscriptions) or as Gold OA. In Greece, researchers find it difficult to publish OA due to the high cost, while the third most important reason why they do not upload their works in institutional repositories is the feeling of uncertainty about whether it is allowed [23].

Finally, a study by Erickson and Stobo (2024) focuses in particular on researchers' experience of Technological Protection Measures (TPMs) applied by publishers and vendors ostensibly to protect their copyrights. The study however underlines that this is often done so clumsily that institutions and individual researchers would prefer to avoid acquiring material protected by TPMs than trying to circumvent them. Both the legal uncertainty and the problematic servicing of their claims by rightsholders deter them from doing so.

4.2. Perceptions and opinions of Greek researchers

In order to understand whether similar phenomena are encountered in the Greek environment, we conducted a survey among Greek researchers. We addressed a call for participation to all possible types of organizations that conduct research, both public and private. The survey was designed to be anonymous, short, and targeted, so that there would be a wide representation. Our experience shows that while knowledge might differ (and in the case of matters pertaining to intellectual property might be very low), the overall perception of a situation is often much more widely shared. The survey, which can be found in the Appendix, was administered digitally, through the Open-Source platform FormBricks, and consisted of the following parts:

- Section 1 – Description of the sample: Type of institution, Scientific field, Familiarity with policies and legislation.
- Section 2 – Areas of evidence:
 - 2a. Access and Re-use enabling and prohibiting factors.
 - 2b. Harmonization & regional necessities.
 - 2c. Partnership with Private Industries.
 - 2d. Academic freedom and Legal certainty.

The survey was distributed in May 2025, lasted three weeks and received 346 full responses in total. It is unclear how many total recipients there were, but this represents 65.77% of the total responses started. There were also 180 unfinished responses (34.23%). These have not been used in our study, even though to a great degree they were usable up to section 2c.

In several of the graphs below we opt for presenting the singular replies of respondents as units, rather than as aggregated rates and scores. Since many of the questions were rating ones, this creates the problem of the visibility of identical responses. To address this and design the visualizations, data are handled with the jittering technique. Aggregated scores have been used when the respondents could select multiple choices. Where possible, inferential statistics have been used to identify differences among the groups of respondents.

4.2.1. Description of the sample

The majority of the respondents were from academic institutions (76.9%), followed by research centers (15.9%). Only three respondents came from start-ups and spin-off companies, while nine came from industry & enterprise. One of the respondents that mentioned “Other” came from an incubator of start-up companies, while the rest stated that are generally researchers from the public and the private sectors.

Organization ■ Academic Institution ■ Enterprise/Industry ■ Other ■ Research Center ■ Spin Off ■ Start Up

Figure 1: Respondents by organization type.

We followed the classification of scientific fields that the EESC uses in other surveys and reports. This scheme classifies researchers into seven broad categories, namely Natural Sciences, Economics & Management, Humanities, Environmental Sciences, Engineering & Technology, Health Sciences and Social Sciences.

Scientific field ■ Economics & Management ■ Engineering & Technology ■ Environmental Sciences ■ Health Sciences ■ Humanities ■ Natural Sciences ■ Social Sciences

Figure 2: Respondents by scientific field.

The largest single share of respondents came from the Engineering & Technology field (23%). Second were respondents from Humanities and Social

Sciences. Most of the respondents from these two fields (who combined represent 35% of the replies) came from academic institutions. The two respondents from start-ups were working in the fields of Environmental Sciences and Engineering & Technology, while the one from a spin-off was working on Health Sciences. Six out of the nine participants from industry were from the Engineering & Technology field.

Participants in the survey seemed to be relatively familiar with the policies of their institutions. This was the case across all types of organizations at averages that range between 48.3 and 55.3% of respondents reporting such familiarity. Awareness of legislative requirements follows, with national laws being known by 90 respondents and European laws by 85. European legislation is known among participants in research centers at a rate of 21%, whereas the national legislation is known by 19.26% of the respondents in academic institutions. Funders' policies were the least well-known, although this cannot be considered as a prerequisite for all kinds of researchers, especially to those from the Humanities and Social Sciences, who have few funders. These were complemented by six responses of "Other" types of policies, which referred mostly to sectoral ones, such as those implemented in projects and networks in which respondents take part.

Figure 3: Familiarity with legislation and policies.

4.2.2. Access and Re-use: enabling and prohibiting factors

In order to understand the situation that they can be in, we asked our sample two questions: "How important is it to have access to digital information (ejournals, ebooks, datasets, etc.) for your research?" (a scale of 1-5) and "How frequent is it to need access to scientific information, but you it is impossible?" (a scale of 1-7). Higher rates in both would signify an urgency; a situation that appears often and affects severely a critical operation. The results of these two questions are combined in Figure 4.

Having access to scientific information is very important for all. Researchers from academic institutions value access at an average of 4.85 (out of five). They were closely followed by their colleagues in research centers with an average of 4.84. All the responses from spin-offs and start-ups were highest, but the lowest average was from enterprise & industry, see 4.72. The few responses with low scores (below 4) came from health scientists in universities.

Figure 4: The importance of finding information compared to the frequency of not being able to access it.

Being unable to access information when needed is a quite frequent phenomenon. All scientific fields recorded average rates above the middle of the scale with Humanities having a score of 5.4 and Health 5.04 (out of seven). The lowest score was from Environmental Scientists with 3.59. In terms of organization types, researchers from enterprise & industry and the generic “other” reported the average rates with 4.67 and 5, respectively. In the two most populated groups, universities and research centers, these average rates were 4.64 and 4.25, respectively.

A subsequent focused on the kind of barriers that they most often encountered. Respondents had several options that reflected financial, technical, and legal constraints, given our acknowledgement that the problems in accessing information cannot necessarily be attributed to any one factor. Figure 5 shows the replies to this, excluding two replies for “Other” and one for “None”. Financial barriers, in the form of paywalls around protected information, are the most common. These are consistently reported across all scientific fields. The option of non-central systems (i.e., a lack of centralized and transparent points of reference for accessing content), was the second most favored one, followed by options for the limits and the relevance of material and systems. These were suggested

mostly by researchers from the Humanities with the two replies for “Other” barriers referring to issues associated with software and equipment and came from the Engineering & Technology and the Economics & Management fields.

Figure 5: The most common barriers to accessing information.

We then asked participants a similar pair of questions regarding the sharing of information: “How important is it for your research to share your own work?” and “How frequently you want to share your scientific information with peers/students, but you cannot?” The need to share scientific information is stronger in research centers and in enterprise & industry, with an average of 4.67 each, followed by academic institutions with 4.61. The scientific disciplines that most reported needing to share scientific information were Natural and Health Sciences, with an average of 4.71 and 4.68 respectively (out of five), while the lowest average was recorded for Economics & Management, at 4.31.

Researchers from academic institutions replied that they are frequently unable to share with an average of 3.9 (out of seven) while their peers from research centers had an average of 3.31. A higher average rate, 4.31, was observed for those in “Other” organizations. Researchers in Health Sciences had an average of 4.3, followed by those in Social Sciences with 4.13, whereas researchers in Economics & Management were the only ones below the middle of the scale, at 3.31.

Respondents also answered a question about the barriers they meet in sharing information. Figure 6 displays those most regularly identified as prohibiting factors, excluding eight replies for “Other”, four for “None” and one for “Do not Know”. The contracts that researchers sign with publishers are the most frequent factors. Other factors that prohibit the sharing of information are the lack of Open Licensing options, the lack of clear information, and legal uncertainty. Six out of the eight responses for “Other” mentioned financial factors, including the costs of OA, which are generally unattainable for many authors, especially for those that are not covered by open access agreements.

Figure 6: The most common barriers to sharing information.

4.2.3. Harmonization & regional necessities

Taking as a given that the research environment in the country is not easily comparable to those in other countries, especially to the so called “advanced” ones that risk drawing away Greek researchers, we asked “How better do you believe are the terms that your collaborators abroad have when it comes to access to and sharing of information compared to yours?” As shown in Figure 7, far more than half (the blue dotted line) of respondents believed that the terms of conducting research in other countries in regard to access to and sharing of information were more advantageous.

Figure 7: Perception of the conditions of research abroad.

The reasons that they think that these conditions differ are mainly connected to systems of rewards and incentives and institutional policies. The selection of the factors shows an appreciation of the impact of policies (both institutional and national), leaving national legislation in fourth place. The respondents also gave 20 “Other” replies, focusing mostly on financial factors, access to content and services and infrastructures in those countries.

Figure 8: Perceived reasons of the different research contexts.

4.2.4. *Partnership between Public and Private Stakeholders*

The next set of questions focused on the conditions in PPPs. We were aiming at understanding perceptions about these, given their role in enabling experimental research that companies may not undertake on their own. Although there are many formal links between the two sectors, the actual conditions differ and there is no formal framework for the circulation of information sources among all researchers involved in partnerships.

The sample was asked “How easy it is to cooperate with a private/public stakeholder for research purposes?”, with mean overall score of 3.98. All STEM scientific fields rated these conditions as favourable (>4), but those in HSS gave lower ones – 3.81 for Humanities and 3.75 for Social Sciences. Public institutions think that they can easily collaborate with their private counterparts, but private ones have rated this easiness below average (see enterprise& industry 3.11).

Figure 9: Distribution of scores for the ease of collaborating in PPPs by organization type.

The follow up question was “How easy is it to have access to and reuse the same information sources with a private/public stakeholder.” The perceptions differ, as the mean rate is 3.7, with enterprise & industry stakeholders rating it at 2.78, followed by the other group with 3.23. The rates of public organizations are also closer to the medium of the scale, as the rates of academic institutions and research centers are 3.76 and 3.67, respectively. All scientific disciplines rated this question above the medium of the scale with the highest being 3.94 for the Environmental Sciences and the lowest 3.52 for the Health Sciences.

Figure 10: Distribution of scores for ease to share and reuse information by organization type.

4.2.5. Academic freedom and Legal certainty

The next set of questions concentrated on the freedom of researchers to act upon their own interests and the certainty to do so. We think that legal certainty is a factor that regulates academic freedom; therefore, the participants were asked “How certain you are to reuse the information you have produced.” As Figure 11 indicates, this was received positively, as the majority of the scores were above 4. In fact, in most of the scientific fields and organization types it was rated above the middle of the scale, with notable cases the low mean scores for enterprise & industry (especially in Engineering & Technology) and “other.”

Figure 11: Distribution of scores for certainty to reuse information/data by organization type.

The participants were also asked “How certain are you when reusing information/data that you have retrieved?” and the answers were similarly positive. Most of scientific disciplines and organization types appear to be very certain with only two exceptions: researchers from enterprise & industry, especially the ones from Engineering & Technology, as well as Health Science researchers from the “other” category reported that they do not feel firmly certain, reporting mean rates of 3.83 and 3.67 respectively.

Figure 12: Distribution of scores for certainty to share information/data by organization type.

When asking for alternatives that would boost their confidence in access to and reuse of scientific information, the participants pointed to funder and institutional policies. The participants made a few other comments, such as the need to be better informed about legislation and the economic support for open research, the possibility to consult an expert about these topics, the demand for changes in the “obsolete” way of publishing research outcomes in closed environments and the need for changes in the research mentality, especially in the Social Sciences.

Figure 13: Alternative measures to improve the context.

Participants had the opportunity to share additional comments, which provided valuable insights. Many of the respondents focused on the removal of bureaucratic hurdles and the simplification of research administration. The fact that the administrative effort is disproportionate to the actual conduct of research is common complaint made by researchers. One researcher from the field of Social Sciences mentioned:

“ If bureaucratic obstacles are not removed, things will worsen.

Some, like the following researcher from Health Sciences, believe that people in the administration are not well equipped to manage research.

“ We should have better information from the right people and not from irrelevant politicians or let politicians have properly trained advisors.

Similarly, one researcher from the field of Engineering & Technology expressed his/her distrust in the leadership of the system.

“ At the National Level, very few people are familiar with research and innovation support issues.

Researchers that raised the matter of financial support were similarly vocal. Many asked for more funding for access to information and data, while a few others concentrated on funding for human resources and equipment. Funds to pay open access fees are now in constant demand, while one researcher asked for an increase of budget of the National Research funding bodies. One researcher underlined concern about minimal research funding and the lack of planning for research:

“ The money given for research is minimal and combined with the lack of central planning for research, this money equals zero. We produce science and live on scraps and sometimes we put money in from our own pockets.

An interesting set of comments was about the regulatory forces at work in research. One researcher from the Humanities raised the matter of harmonization and the fact that a lack of this then combines with the cultural traits of the communities.

“ It is difficult to find the internal regulations of organizations and to understand how legal restrictions interact with “etiquette” restrictions.

Another researcher from the Natural Sciences highlighted the fact that there is no legal framework for protecting the intellectual work carried out by public institutions.

“ There is no serious framework in Greece for intellectual property produced by public bodies. In other countries (USA, UK, etc.) there is a clear and structured policy for work produced in public bodies, which protects the intellectual property rights of the bodies and scientists who produce them, as well as of the state.

Another participant focused on the contradictions between the willingness to enjoy open access to information and the actual situation, explaining its outcomes.

“ ...I personally see an insurmountable contradiction between the theoretical framework that suggests that research is accessible to people who wish to do so, while in the lived reality the tools for carrying out such a thing do not exist.

If the resources are not there, the legitimate result cannot be achieved, which I personally consider dangerous!

One of the participants from the field of Engineering & Technology doubted the sincerity of motives regarding the dissemination of information.

“ Both access to information (e.g., publishing houses, libraries, organizations issuing guidelines/regulations) and dissemination of information (conferences, open access journals, patents, etc.) have purely financial limitations. Of course, if the research subject is promising for commercial exploitation, dissemination is not particularly important or is done ostensibly in order to satisfy the relevant requirements of the funding program.

A researcher from the Environmental Sciences, while applauding open access, asked for measures to ensure data protection:

“ Written consent from copyright owners for the use of their data in research should be applied, and the metadata of the data should be made public, not the data itself.

It is to be noted that, given that data itself is not subject copyright, the last statement arguably underlines the need for further legal literacy in this space.

4.3. Conclusions

The results of this study highlight the difficulties encountered in accessing information: despite the content supplied by HEAL-Link, which is the main provider of scholarly information to all academic and research institutes, the resources available are neither enough nor entirely relevant. Furthermore, information overload and the disparity of resources and infrastructures create uncertainty as to where and how to address questions, either concerning access or publishing. As the academic and research environment expands and the indicators of production rise, researchers need wide access to information on a variety of topics. Innovation cannot be driven only by the traditional fields but lies also in the needs of novel and multidisciplinary knowledge domains. One researcher mentioned that “In the field of graphic design as well as those of 2D animation, 3D animation, and gaming, there are few sources and research at this stage is in its infancy.”

Accessing and sharing information are two sides of the same coin and are essential to the progress of science and research. The results show that barriers to both of these lie mainly in financial and legal factors, both rooted in publishers' practices. The respondents mention a frequent need to be able to access the right information, but to be unable to do so. This underlines problems with the current model of subscribed content that is provided by scientific publishers through the libraries, at a time that the library sector in Greece is ageing and shrinking, leaving some universities and research centers to run their libraries with as few as one person. Systems that are supposed to support the circulation of information are not able to fulfil this role, and in the absence of credible advice on how it is best

to retrieve, use, publish, and reuse information (and short of reforms to bring greater simplicity), researchers find themselves unable to manage these tasks effectively.

Sharing information is also affected by publishers' practices, namely contracts of exclusivity. Authors cannot reuse their own material even for reasons that relate to elementary exceptions, such as research and education, but must rely on the terms of the publishers to allow this after embargo periods and in ways that are not favored in scholarly practices. As they benefit from transformative agreements signed by HEAL-Link and other open access opportunities, they now have as their priority the kind of publications that are supported by article processing charges, another financially based parameter. It is well known however that Gold Open Access raises many concerns about sustainability, despite the large investments. In a limited market, like Greece, which tends to underprivilege fields such as Social Sciences and Humanities, it further enhances inequalities. Having the ability to share information may still be an option but comes at a high cost that is out of the reach of many.

Participants stated a preference in policies; they are familiar with and appreciate them as a condition that can make a difference in the research environment, as they do in other countries. However, at the same time, we see that policies are few, weak and are not exercised consistently and confidently. As noted, none of the RPOs and RFOs are implementing Rights Retention policies that explicitly ask for the keeping of intellectual property rights in a way that secure a good record of their production and enable future reuse.

Participants did not appreciate the lengthy procedures and the complex logistics around research management. This pervasive lack of faith in the system's credibility and its commitment to meritocracy is a significant concern. Respondents suggest that a more equitable system of rewards and compelling incentives could be a key factor in improving the situation. Specifically, the processes for selecting research funding have been marred by various issues, and it is crucial that proper rewards are fundamentally based on meritocracy.

As in other reports of the EESC, it is reconfirmed that a great amount of workforce for support and orientation for researchers is missing. Researchers need technologically, scholarly, and legally savvy support staff that will guide them to take the best decisions. The same personnel could also monitor the implementation of policies, but just are not there in the numbers needed.

Participants from enterprise & industry seem to face difficulties in collaborating with their public institutions' peers. This is confirmed by the country's EIS profile and the weak linkages between the private and the public sectors. Currently there is no clear overview of the private sector's perceptions about openness, which in many cases is associated with economic activity in cutting-edge products and markets [25]. Much more certainty is needed to find the proper balance between openness that will further develop knowledge and protection that will give an advantage.

5. Recommendations

We group the recommendations according to some principles that should characterize the research ecosystem of Greece.

Clarity: The State has to take initiatives to establish practices that maximize the free circulation of knowledge inside and outside of the country. An outward-looking culture and internationalization are key drivers the policies in the academic and research domains, but practices around the management of research outputs are currently do not contribute to this.

The existence and implementation of top-down policies and/or legislation should not be seen as a factor that limits academic freedom, rather than as an instrument that coordinates the best possible availability and reuse of knowledge. Furthermore, reforming copyright laws around research (both for uses and outputs) in order to align them with research policy goals (including the strengthening of partnerships) could also help give clarity and reassurance.

Determination: The current European framework is providing a first-class opportunity for Greece to update its approach and to transform into a country that favors openness and fosters innovation. Visionary policy making is strongly supported by the Draghi and Letta reports, as well as several other EU developments, such as the upcoming ERA Act and conclusions of the Council of European Union, that together constitute a framework of which other countries take advantage of in order to build competitiveness.

Confidence would be supported by RPOs and RFOs introducing and implementing Open Science policies that focus on benefits to the research community, rather than any other third party. There is convincing evidence about the value of Rights Retention policies from other countries that could pave the way for Greek organizations to do the same.

The State needs to invest in and improve the research support environment with knowledgeable and skilled staff, as well as with modern, interoperable infrastructures that truly digitally transform processes and outcomes.

Balance: Central and regional research and innovation councils, as well as all other policy making institutions in this extraordinarily complex system should create opportunities for a dialogue between the public and private sectors so that research flows from and to both ends easily, and as quickly as possible. Protectionism has been proven to be an overly conservative measure that leads to stagnation in the production of new knowledge. With the advancement of Open Science policies that support balanced approaches between openness and security, the research ecosystem can present more opportunities.

The legislative framework for science and innovation should incorporate provisions for an SPR, as the bare minimum of independence and legal certainty for authors. This is expected to assist the country in increasing its open access

scores (especially the Green one) and provide new opportunities for openness and its benefits. KR21 has developed a model article for SPR for Greece that would strengthen the position of researchers and rebalance fundamental rights and obligations:

“ The author of a work in a scientific journal or in a collective volume is entitled to make it available to the public in any definitive edition through any non-profit open access repository immediately after publication, including any third-party content, such as images and tables, provided that (a) the research to which the scientific work refers has been covered in whole or in part by public resources; and (b) it is accompanied by an indication of the source and the names of the authors and the publisher, provided that these names are known. Any contrary contractual arrangement is invalid.

Investment in Capacity: Research libraries should be placed centrally in the system, as the hubs that bring together expertise, as well as the opinions of all stakeholders, in order to boost capacity. Service development in research libraries should be collaborative with other units and departments, such as Technology Transfer Offices. They should be able to expand the capacity of the research staff through comprehensive training programmes.

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Appendix

The questionnaire in Greek.

1. Εργάζεστε σε...

Ακαδημαϊκό ίδρυμα, Ερευνητικό κέντρο, Επιχείρηση/Βιομηχανία, Νεοφυή επιχείρηση (start-up), Τεχνοβλαστό (spin-off), Άλλου

2. Θα κατατάσσατε την ερευνητική σας δουλειά στο επιστημονικό πεδίο...

Μηχανική & Τεχνολογία, Ανθρωπιστικές Επιστήμες, Κοινωνικές Επιστήμες, Φυσικές Επιστήμες, Επιστήμες της Υγείας, Οικονομικά & Διοίκηση, Περιβαλλοντικές Επιστήμες

3. Με ποιο από τα παρακάτω είστε περισσότερο εξοικειωμένοι/ές;

Πολιτική του ιδρύματος/κέντρου, Εθνική νομοθεσία για την έρευνα, Ευρωπαϊκή νομοθεσία για την έρευνα, Πολιτική του χρηματοδοτικού φορέα, Άλλο

4. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να έχετε πρόσβαση σε ψηφιακή πληροφορία (ejournals, ebooks, datasets, κλπ.) για την ερευνά σας;

Πολύ σημαντικό, Σημαντικό, Ουδέτερο, Ελάχιστο σημαντικό, Καθόλου σημαντικό

5. Πόσο συχνά θέλετε να έχετε πρόσβαση σε επιστημονική πληροφορία, αλλά δεν μπορείτε να έχετε;

1-7

6. Τι είδους εμπόδια συναντάτε;

Οικονομικής φύσεως (paywalls), Μη κεντρικά συστήματα, Ελάχιστο υλικό/συστήματα, Μη συναφές υλικό/συστήματα, Τεχνικής φύσεως (technological protection measures), Μη έγκυρο υλικό/συστήματα, Άλλο

7. Πόσο σημαντικό για την ερευνά σας είναι να διαμοιράζετε το δικό σας έργο;

Πολύ σημαντικό, Σημαντικό, Ουδέτερο, Ελάχιστο σημαντικό, Καθόλου σημαντικό

8. Πόσο συχνά θέλετε να διαμοιράζετε τη δική σας επιστημονική πληροφορία με συνεργάτες/φοιτητές, αλλά δεν μπορείτε;

1-7

9. Ποιος/οι είναι οι αποτρεπτικοί παράγοντες;

Τα ιδιωτικά συμφωνητικά με τους εκδότες, Η έλλειψη επιλογών για την ανοικτή αδειοδότηση, Η έλλειψη ξεκάθαρης πληροφόρησης, Η νομική αβεβαιότητα, Η έλλειψη αξιόπιστων συστημάτων, Η νομοθεσία ή η πολιτική του φορέα μου, Άλλος

10. Πόσο καλύτεροι πιστεύετε ότι είναι οι όροι με τους οποίους οι συνεργάτες σας στο εξωτερικό έχουν πρόσβαση και διαμοιράζονται πληροφορία σε σχέση με τους δικούς σας;

Πολύ καλύτεροι, Καλύτεροι, Ουδέτεροι, Ελάχιστα καλύτεροι, Καθόλου καλύτεροι

11. Ποιο από τα παρακάτω θεωρείτε ότι τους δίνει πλεονέκτημα;
Διαφορές στα κίνητρα και τις επιβραβεύσεις, Διαφορές στις πολιτικές των φορέων εργασίας, Διαφορές στις εθνικές πολιτικές, Διαφορές στην εθνική νομοθεσία, Άλλο

12. Πόσο εύκολο είναι να συνεργαστείτε με έναν ιδιωτικό/δημόσιο φορέα για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς;
1-7

13. Πόσο εύκολο είναι να έχετε πρόσβαση και να διαμοιραστείτε τους ίδιους πληροφοριακούς πόρους με έναν ιδιωτικό/δημόσιο φορέα;
1-7

14. Πόσο σίγουροι/ές είστε να διαμοιραστείτε την πληροφορία που έχετε παράξει;
1-7

15. Πόσο σίγουροι/ές είστε να επαναχρησιμοποιήσετε τις πληροφορίες/δεδομένα που έχετε ανακτήσει;
1-7

16. Ποιό/ά από τα παρακάτω θα αυξήσει την αυτοπεποίθησή σας για δυνατότητες πρόσβασης και επαναχρησιμοποίησης της επιστημονικής πληροφορίας για την ερευνά σας;
Εφαρμογή πολιτικών των χρηματοδοτικών φορέων, Εφαρμογή πολιτικών των φορέων εργασίας, Αναθεώρηση της εθνικής νομοθεσίας, Αναθεώρηση της Ευρωπαϊκής νομοθεσίας, Άλλο

Executive Summary

This report, commissioned by the Knowledge Rights 21 National Coordinator for Greece, explores the state of research and innovation in Greece in relation to the challenges and opportunities for open access to information. The study was conducted by the Scholarly Communication Unit (EESC) of the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link (HEAL-Link) and had two key objectives, namely, to summarize the legislative framework for research and innovation in Greece and its impact on open knowledge circulation and to provide evidence of the difficulties Greek researchers encounter in their access to and reuse of research information.

A central finding of the report is the highly fragmented and uncoordinated nature of the current system, which hinders the nation's research potential. Existing legislation, often fragmented and in confusing abundance, fails to adequately address the circulation of scientific information and disregards the conditions of its production and the requirements of collaborative research practices.

The survey results reveal that Greek researchers frequently struggle to access timely, sufficient, and relevant information. They also face limitations in sharing information with other stakeholders, including private partners, and express their will for reforms that would align Greece's research environment with international standards.

The report underscores the need for a more open and accessible research environment. It stresses the importance of revising the policy and legal framework to promote the free flow of information, enabling Greek researchers to compete effectively on a European and global scale. This includes actions that address the challenges posed by publisher practices and call for adequate support for libraries and information infrastructures. The report also recommends that all key stakeholders implement effective measures to simplify the ecosystem, promote open science policies, support legislative changes, and advance the development of a vibrant and competitive research ecosystem in Greece.